

PROJECT DETAILS

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Summary

The monitoring of forest disturbances is crucial for understanding ecosystem dynamics, assessing the impacts of climate change, and informing conservation policies. **Deliverable D 2.1** serves as the primary output of Work Package 2 Forest Disturbance Analysis (WP2). It evaluates selected external datasets for forest disturbance detection, focusing on their methodologies, characteristics, and applicability to Mediterranean forest ecosystems. This assessment will serve as a baseline for **harmonization strategies** in Work Package 4 (WP4), which will support **internal product development in Work Package 3 (WP3)**, contributing to the development of more rigorous and effective forest disturbance monitoring approaches.

The selected external datasets include:

1. **Global Forest Change (GFC)** – A global-scale forest monitoring system based on annual tree cover loss detection using **Landsat imagery**.
2. **European Forest Disturbance Atlas (EFDA)** – A **pan-European** disturbance dataset tracking **multiple forest disturbance events per location** from **1985 to the present (2023)**.
3. **Alert and Annual Changes System (AACCS)** – A **national-scale** system for Spain, comprising two datasets:
 - **Monthly and Annual Alerts on Forest Surface (MAAFS)** – Detecting real-time vegetation anomalies using Sentinel-2 imagery.
 - **Annual Changes in Forest Surface (ACFS)** – Providing long-term assessments of forest loss and regeneration.

This deliverable compares the three datasets in terms of spatial and temporal coverage, data sources, classification methods, accuracy, and usability, while also identifying their strengths and limitations.

1 Overview of External datasets

The external datasets were selected for their reliability, accessibility, and relevance in monitoring Mediterranean forest disturbances. Each dataset employs state-of-the-art satellite imagery and validated processing methods, ensuring consistent and accurate tracking of forest changes. These datasets monitor forest disturbances across different geographic scales:

- **Global Forest Change (GFC)** – Global annual deforestation monitoring.
- **European Forest Disturbance Atlas (EFDA)** – Pan-European multi-disturbance tracking.
- **Alert and Annual Changes System (AACS)** – Spain-specific monitoring

This **multi-scale approach** ensures a **comprehensive perspective** on forest change, facilitating **harmonization (WP4)**.

1.1 Key Attributes of External Datasets

To clarify their relevance within WP2, the following table summarizes the main characteristics of each dataset, facilitating their comparative evaluation and integration into the project's forest disturbance analysis framework. Detailed methodological aspects including strengths and weaknesses are in Appendix I.

Product	GFC	EFDA	AACS	
			MAAFS	ACFS
Temporal Coverage	2000 – Present (2023)	1985 – Present (2023)	2019 – 2023	2019 – 2023
Spatial Coverage	Global (excluding Antarctica and some Arctic islands)	Continental Europe (excluding Russia, Malta, Cyprus)	Spain	Spain
Temporal Resolution	Annual (loss), 12-year (gain)	Annual updates	Monthly alerts, annual consolidation	Annual updates

Disturbance Types	Stand replacement disturbances (forest loss), no explicit classification of causes	Fire; Windthrow/bark beetle outbreaks (combined category); Harvest	Fire events; Vegetation vigor loss	Logging; Deforestation; Wildfire Damage; Vegetation Gain
Multiple Disturbance Events per Pixel	No	Yes	No	No
Input Data Used	Landsat (30m), MODIS, LiDAR and independent reference datasets	Landsat 4-9 archive (30m), forest land use and disturbance reference data (20,084 manually interpreted pixels)	Sentinel-2 (10-20m), ancillary land cover data IEPNB, EFFIS, FIRMS and MFE*	Sentinel-2 (10-20m), historical reference data from FF and SIGPAC. IEPNB, EFFIS, FIRMS, MFE,
Algorithm Used for Classification	Decision trees and spectral analysis	Random Forest machine learning classification	NDVI-based anomaly detection refined afterwards	Trend analysis for vegetation gains, frequency-based analysis for losses
Validation Data	MODIS NDVI, LiDAR-derived canopy height and a stratified random sample of 1,500 blocks	Independent stratified random sample of 2500 pixels	-	Manual photointerpretation for selected polygons and comparison with high and medium spatial resolution imagery
Accuracy	99.6% ($\pm 0.7\%$) globally. For <u>forest loss</u> , depending on the region: user's accuracy: 79.3% - 93.9%;	Overall F1-score of 0.89 (disturbance) For the <u>disturbed class</u> : omission error is 22.5% and commission error: 17.3% (drops to 10.6% after 2000)	No direct field validation or manual corrections Annual vegetation loss is detected by consolidating frequent monthly	Overall classification accuracy of changes is $\geq 80\%$ at the provincial level, applied as a validation threshold across all change categories.

	producer's accuracy: 79.4% - 93.9%.		alerts for greater accuracy.	
MMU	30m (0.09 ha, Landsat pixel)	0.27 ha (3 Landsat pixels)	25x25m pixels (IEPNB grid)	0.5 ha (aggregation of 8 pixels)
Reference System (EPSG)	EPSG:4326 (WGS 84)	EPSG:3035 (ETRS89/LAEA Europe)	EPSG:25830 (Peninsular Spain & Balearic), EPSG:32628 (Canary Islands)	EPSG:25830 (Peninsular Spain & Balearic), EPSG:32628 (Canary Islands)
Output Details	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tree canopy cover for year 2000 • Global forest cover gain 2000-2012 • Year of gross forest cover loss event • Data mask (no data, land surface, water). • Circa year 2000 Circa year 2023 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest land use mask • Annual disturbances • Disturbance probability • Latest disturbance year • Greatest disturbance year • Number of disturbances • Disturbance severity • Disturbance agent (annual) • Aggregated disturbance agent over time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly Alerts for 2023 • Annual Alerts for 2023 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified Annual Alerts of year: Gain • Classified Annual Alerts of year: Losses
Open Access	Fully open-access	Fully open-access	Monthly alerts: (available upon request)	Fully open-access

			Annual alerts: Fully open-access	
Mask Used (forest/non-forest)	Tree cover threshold (>30%) applied globally	European-wide forest mask based on historical Landsat data and LUCAS field survey	Forest areas are defined based on the most updated version of the MFE	Forest areas are defined based on the most updated version of the MFE

*Note: IEPNB (Spanish Inventory of Natural Heritage and Biodiversity), EFFIS (European Forest Fire Information System), FIRMS (Fire Information for Resource Management System), Spanish Forest Map (Mapa Forestal de España - MFE), SIGPAC (Spanish Geographic Information System for Agricultural Parcel).

1.2 Strengths and Limitations of External datasets

The following section presents a **comparative analysis of the most relevant strengths and limitations** for **WP2**. This comparison highlights their unique contributions, as well as challenges related to forest disturbance detection. A detailed breakdown of the **methodological strengths and weaknesses** of each dataset can be found in **Appendix I**.

Shared Strengths

- All datasets employ satellite-based observations for standardized monitoring.
- Automated workflows enhance scalability and reproducibility.
- GFC and EFDA use Landsat (30m resolution), while AACS utilizes Sentinel-2 (10–20m resolution) for national-scale assessments.
- Open-access availability (except MAAFS monthly alerts, which require a request).
- Multi-temporal capabilities enable trend analysis.

Unique Strengths

- **GFC** excels in **global deforestation monitoring**, providing annual forest loss tracking at a worldwide scale since 2000.
- **EFDA** is unique in its ability to **classify specific disturbance types** (fire, windthrow/ bark beetle outbreaks (combined category), harvest), making it particularly valuable for understanding Mediterranean forest dynamics. It also is the only dataset capable of tracking multiple disturbance events per pixel over time, a capability that significantly enhances its ability to monitor recurring disturbances and short-rotation harvests. This feature allows 30–40% more disturbances to be detected compared to previous datasets (Hansen et al. 2013, Senf & Seidl 2021a, Turubanova et al. 2023). Approximately 28% of all disturbed pixels in Europe have experienced multiple disturbance events, further demonstrating EFDA's ability to capture complex forest dynamics.

- **AACS (both MAAFS and ACSF)** is specifically tailored to Spanish forests, ensuring better detection of subtle changes in Mediterranean Forest, unlike global or European-wide datasets.
- **MAAFS (AACS)** stands out for near real-time detection, offering monthly alerts that facilitate rapid response to disturbances in Spain. Notably, it offers a robust classification of wildfire events. The integration of EFFIS, FIRMS, and BAIS2 enhances the accuracy of fire disturbance detection, minimizing misclassification errors. However, it does not track multiple disturbances per pixel; instead, it consolidates anomalies into annual summaries.
- **ACFS (AACS)** enables structured national monitoring of both forest loss and regeneration, aligning with Spain's official forest inventories and long-term conservation efforts.

Challenges and Limitations

- **Disturbance Cause Attribution:** None of the datasets comprehensively differentiate between all disturbance types (e.g., fire, logging, storms, pests), limiting their ecological interpretability. EFDA can classify specific disturbance types like fire and harvest but faces challenges distinguishing windthrow from bark beetle, so both categories are merged into one combined category.
- **Low-Severity Disturbance Detection:** Due to reliance on spectral change detection, gradual disturbances such as selective logging or canopy degradation are often missed or underestimated.
- **Limitations in Detecting Disturbances in Sparse Vegetation and Semi-Arid Ecosystems:** Detecting disturbances in low-density vegetation ecosystems, such as Mediterranean forests, semi-arid landscapes, and early regrowth areas, presents classification challenges. The dominance of exposed soil in spectral signals increases the likelihood of misclassifying both forest loss and recovery, leading to over- or underestimation of vegetation change. Seasonal NDVI fluctuations in Mediterranean and semi-arid areas may be misinterpreted as permanent changes, affecting classification accuracy. Small-scale disturbances like selective logging, understory removal, and gradual canopy decline are often overlooked due to subtle spectral variations. Misclassification remains a challenge in regions with high vegetation heterogeneity and dynamic ground cover changes.
- **Cloud Cover and Seasonal Variability:** Persistent cloud cover interferes with observations across all datasets, particularly in humid and mountainous Mediterranean regions, affecting disturbance classification reliability.
- **Resolution Constraints:** GFC and EFDA's 30m resolution can limit their ability to detect small-scale changes, while AACS benefits from Sentinel-2's 10–20m resolution but still struggles with detecting early-stage vegetation recovery.
- **Temporal Consistency Issues:** Methodological updates and sensor transitions create inconsistencies in long-term data series, complicating historical trend analysis and harmonization.

- **Forest Gain Detection Challenges:** GFC and AACS struggle with accurately identifying regrowth, often misclassifying early-stage vegetation recovery.

2 Conclusion

2.1 Key Findings

WP2 establishes a foundational assessment of external datasets for forest disturbance monitoring, identifying key strengths and limitations that inform subsequent project activities:

- **GFC provides global consistency** for large-scale deforestation monitoring (showing higher reliability in boreal and temperate regions compared to the tropics) , but its application to Mediterranean forests requires adaptation due to its stand-replacement disturbance definition and lack of disturbance cause attribution.
- **EFDA offers thematic precision** by classifying specific disturbance types (fire, windthrow/ bark beetle outbreaks (combined category), harvest), making it particularly valuable for monitoring Mediterranean forest dynamics. However, it faces challenges distinguishing windthrow from bark beetle outbreaks. It also uniquely captures multiple disturbance events per pixel, setting it apart from other datasets that focus on single-event detection or annual aggregation. This capability enables the detection of recurrent logging activities, successive wildfires, and overlapping natural and anthropogenic disturbances, making it the most comprehensive dataset for monitoring European forest dynamics. The inclusion of multiple disturbances per pixel also enhances EFDA's accuracy and provides a more detailed representation of forest change compared to alternative datasets
- **MAAFS delivers high-resolution, near real-time monitoring**, providing monthly updates that enable a rapid response to disturbances in Spain. It is particularly effective in detecting abrupt changes, such as wildfire damage, but its automated classification system may generate false positives in areas with strong seasonal vegetation variability.
- **ACFS provides a structured** annual monitoring framework that aligns with **national** forest inventories, ensuring consistency in tracking forest loss and regeneration trends. However, its reliance on yearly updates limits its ability to detect short-term disturbances, necessitating integration with higher-frequency datasets like MAAFS for more comprehensive monitoring.

2.2 Implications for WP3, and WP4

The findings from WP2 will directly inform the following work packages:

- **WP3: Internal Product Development** – The strengths and weaknesses of external datasets will guide the selection of methodologies for internal product creation. Understanding

dataset limitations (e.g., temporal inconsistencies, resolution constraints) ensures that internal products complement and improve upon existing monitoring efforts.

- **WP4: Harmonization Strategies** – The variability in spatial resolution, classification methods and classified categories, and update frequency among datasets, underscores the need for a robust harmonization framework. The lessons learned from this assessment will be critical in aligning external and internal products to ensure consistency.

2.3 Challenges and Recommendations

This analysis identifies key challenges in Mediterranean forest disturbance monitoring, which will inform subsequent work packages:

- **Detecting subtle disturbances** – Mediterranean forests often experience gradual canopy changes besides abrupt deforestation (conversion of forested land to non-forested land), requiring refined classification methods.
- **Data integration issues** – Differences in spatial resolution and update frequency between datasets may introduce inconsistencies that need to be addressed in WP4's harmonization process.

To address these challenges, **WP3 and WP4 should prioritize:**

- Developing **optimized classification thresholds** tailored for Mediterranean forests.
- Ensuring **harmonization with external datasets** to enhance comparability and usability.
- Implementing **a structured validation process** which includes high-resolution reference data among other reference data.

2.4 Final Remarks

By ensuring validation accuracy and methodological consistency, this deliverable contributes to the broader project objective of generating **statistically rigorous and validated disturbance maps for Mediterranean forests**. The insights gained from this evaluation will support the development of improved forest monitoring methodologies and facilitate informed decision-making for conservation and management efforts.

3 APPENDIX I

The extensive methodological details on dataset processing, including imagery data processing, used algorithm, and accuracy assessment details for each dataset, have been streamlined and placed here. The main text focuses on comparative insights that support WP3 and WP4, while the appendix retains detailed technical explanations for reference.

3.1 Global Forest Change (GFC)

The **Global Forest Change (GFC)** dataset, developed by the **Global Land Analysis and Discovery (GLAD) lab at the University of Maryland**, provides an **annually updated global-scale forest loss dataset** based on **Landsat satellite imagery**. The dataset enables the monitoring of forest extent and change from **2000 to the present (2023)**, offering a **high-resolution, globally consistent** approach to tracking deforestation and forest disturbances.

Originally developed by **Hansen et al. (2013)**, the methodology has evolved over time, incorporating **advancements in satellite technology, data processing algorithms, and classification models**. The latest version, **GFC-2023 v1.11**, introduces key updates, including **the integration of Landsat 8 and 9 data, enhanced training datasets, and improved per-sensor quality assessments**.

3.1.1 Methodology

The methodology used in the **GFC dataset** follows a structured process based on **time-series analysis of Landsat satellite imagery** to detect forest cover loss at **30-meter spatial resolution**. The process can be divided into the following **key steps** (Hansen, et al 2013):

1. Forest Definition and Change Criteria

- **Forest Definition:** Forest areas are classified as regions with tree canopy cover **≥30%** (proportion of a Landsat pixel (30m resolution) occupied by tree canopy) and vegetation height **≥5 meters**. These criteria provided a globally consistent definition of forest that worked across different climates and ecosystems while remaining comparable to other datasets. The study stratified results by tree cover percentage categories (e.g., >50% crown cover to ~0% crown cover).
- **Forest Loss:** Defined as a **stand-replacement disturbance**, meaning the complete removal of tree canopy at the 30m pixel scale. The methodology does **not** track forest degradation but rather full canopy loss.
- **Forest Gain:** Defined as the transition from a **non-forest** to a **forest state**, representing persistent regrowth exceeding the **30% canopy cover threshold**.

1. Data Collection and Preprocessing

- **Study Area Selection:** The analysis covered all global land except Antarctica and some Arctic islands.
- **Satellite Data Acquisition:** The dataset is derived from **Landsat 5, 7, 8, and 9** imagery to track forest change metrics.
 - **Initially (2000-2012)**, analysis primarily relied on **Landsat 7 Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+)**. **From 2013 onward, Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI)** was integrated, enhancing spectral analysis. **Since 2022, Landsat 9 OLI** has been incorporated for further improvements in data quality. The **OLI on Landsat 8 and 9** has a **higher signal-to-noise ratio** than previous Landsat sensors, enhancing change detection.
 - The **global acquisition strategy** has significantly improved, with available Landsat images increasing from under **150,000 per year in the early 2000s** to **over 250,000 per year in recent years**.
- **Preprocessing and Data Normalization:**
 - **Top of Atmosphere (TOA) Reflectance Calibration:** Converts raw digital numbers into reflectance values.
 - **Cloud, Shadow, and Water Masking:** Atmospheric and environmental noise filtering using automated algorithms.
 - **Geometric and Radiometric Corrections:** Sensor differences across different time periods are corrected.
 - **Best-Available-Pixel (BAP) Compositing:** Uses **median** spectral observations from growing season data across four Landsat bands (**Red, Near-Infrared (NIR), Shortwave Infrared 1 (SWIR1), and Shortwave Infrared 2 (SWIR2)**).

2. Feature Extraction and Spectral Analysis

- **Time-Series Spectral Metrics Calculation:**
 - Three types of per-band spectral metrics are extracted:
 - Maximum, minimum, and selected percentile reflectance values.
 - Mean reflectance values for different percentile intervals.
 - Slope of linear regression for reflectance vs. time to track spectral trends.
- **Training Data Collection:**
 - Training datasets were generated using **high-resolution satellite imagery** (e.g., QuickBird, Google Earth), **Existing Landsat-Derived Percent Tree Cover Datasets** (e.g., by the University of Maryland), and **MODIS global tree cover datasets** rescaled to match Landsat resolution.
 - Manual interpretation of image samples was used to define training areas as **forest/no-forest**, generating reference points for classification.

3. Classification and Forest Change Detection

- **Decision-Tree-Based Classification:**
 - A bagged decision tree classifier was trained using the spectral metrics and training data. The model classified each Landsat pixel based on changes in spectral signals over time.
 - Change detection is based on: **Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI):** Identifies vegetation health and canopy loss. **Shortwave Infrared Reflectance (SWIR):** Detects disturbances such as fire, logging, and deforestation.
- **Forest Loss Detection:**
 - Forest loss is mapped **annually** from **2000 to 2023** using the **decision-tree classification model**.
 - A **set of heuristics** was applied to determine the **maximum annual decline in percent tree cover** and **minimum growing season NDVI** to pinpoint forest loss events.
 - A **Loss Year Layer** indicates the first year a pixel was classified as forest loss.
- **Forest Gain Detection:**
 - Gain is assessed **cumulatively (2000–2020)** rather than annually.
 - Tree cover regrowth beyond the **30% threshold** is mapped, but gain detection remains **less frequent than loss detection**.
 - NDVI and SWIR time-series analysis confirm sustained regrowth rather than seasonal fluctuations.
- **Data Processing at Continental Scale:** To enhance **efficiency**, the analysis was conducted **separately** for North America, South America, Eurasia, Africa, and Australia.

4. Validation and Accuracy Assessment

- **Independent Sample-Based Validation:**
 - A **stratified random sample of 1,500 blocks (120m² each)** was used for validation.
 - Sampling was stratified by **biome type (boreal, temperate, humid tropical, dry tropical, and other land types)** and **change category (no change, loss, gain)** (150 blocks per biome for no change, 90 blocks for loss, 60 blocks for gain).
- **Reference Data Collection:**
 - Each validation sample was manually interpreted using: **Landsat time-series imagery, MODIS NDVI time-series, High-resolution imagery from Google Earth**.
 - The percentage of gain or loss per sample block was recorded in quartiles (**0, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, or 1**).
- **Comparison of Map and Reference Data:**
 - **Forest loss validation: Map-estimated loss: 2.3M km² vs. Validation estimate: 2.2M km²; strong agreement.**

- **Forest gain validation: Map-estimated gain: 0.8M km² vs. Validation estimate: 0.9M km²**; slight underestimation.
- **Annual Forest Loss Timing Validation:**
 - MODIS NDVI was used to validate the year of detected disturbances.
 - **75.2% of loss events matched the correct year**, and **96.7% fell within ±1 year**.
- **Additional Validation Using LiDAR (GLAS Data):**
 - NASA's **GLAS LiDAR** assessed **tree height changes** before and after loss events.
 - The difference in canopy height before and after disturbance confirmed classification accuracy.
- The accuracy assessment according to Hansen, et al 2013, indicated high overall accuracy across different biomes, with forest loss detection achieving an overall accuracy of **99.6% (±0.7%) globally**. **User's accuracy** for **forest loss ranges** between **79.3% and 93.9%**, while **producer's accuracy** varies between **79.4% and 93.9%**, depending on the region. **Forest gain** detection, however, shows more variability, with **user's accuracy** ranging from **62.0% to 85.5%** and **producer's accuracy** between **48.0% and 98.4%**, reflecting challenges in detecting regrowth dynamics. The **highest accuracy levels** were recorded in **boreal and temperate regions**, while **tropical forests** exhibited **greater variability**, particularly in **forest gain** classification.
- **Uncertainty Considerations**
 - **Users are cautioned against relying on raw pixel counts** for absolute area estimations.
 - The **Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)** recommends **probability-based statistical methods** for estimating land-use change areas.
 - **Temporal filtering (e.g., 3-year moving average)** is recommended to discern trends over time.

5. Algorithm Refinements (Version 1.11 Updates)

- **Use of Landsat 8 OLI data for 2013 onward and Landsat 9 OLI for 2022 onward**, improving spectral sensitivity and image consistency.
- **Reprocessed data from 2011 onward to** enhance interannual consistency in forest loss detection.
- **Refined training data for calibrating the loss model**, leading to more accurate classification.
- **Enhanced per-sensor quality assessment models** to filter low-quality input data.
- **Improved input spectral features**, incorporating refined vegetation and disturbance indicators for better classification.
- **More accurate detection of boreal forest loss due to fire**, improving sensitivity to disturbance events.
- **Better identification of smallholder rotational agricultural clearing**, particularly in dry and humid tropical forests.

- **Enhanced detection of selective logging**, refining the ability to differentiate partial removals from clear-cutting.
- **Improved detection of short-cycle plantation** clearing in sub-tropical and tropical ecozones.
- **Transition phase toward** GFC v2.0, with plans to harmonize the full 2000-onward dataset in future releases.

5. Final Product Layers

This global dataset is divided into 10x10 degree tiles, consisting of seven files per tile. All files contain unsigned 8-bit values and have a **spatial resolution of 1 arc-second per pixel**, or approximately **30 meters per pixel at the equator**. Only **lossyear** and **last** are updated annually.

- **Tree canopy cover for year 2000** (*treecover2000*): Tree cover in the year 2000, defined as canopy closure for all vegetation taller than 5m in height. Encoded as a percentage per output grid cell, in the range 0-100.
- **Global forest cover gain 2000-2012 (gain)**: Forest gain during the period 2000-2012, defined as the inverse of loss, or a non-forest to forest change entirely within the study period. Encoded as either 1 (gain) or 0 (no gain).
- **Year of gross forest cover loss event (lossyear)**: Forest loss during the period 2000-2023, defined as a stand-replacement disturbance, or a change from a forest to non-forest state. Encoded as either 0 (no loss) or else a value in the range 1-23, representing loss detected primarily in the year 2001-2023, respectively.
- **Data mask (datamask)**: Three values representing areas of no data (0), mapped land surface (1), and persistent water bodies (2) based on 2000-2012.
- **Circa year 2000 Landsat 7 cloud-free image composite (first)**: Reference multispectral imagery from the first available year, typically 2000. If no cloud-free observations were available for the year 2000, imagery was taken from the closest year with cloud-free data, within the range 1999-2012.
- **Circa year 2023 Landsat cloud-free image composite (last)**: Reference multispectral imagery from the last available year, typically 2023. If no cloud-free observations were available for the year 2023, imagery was taken from the closest year with cloud-free data.

6. Access

The GFC dataset is **openly accessible to the public**, providing comprehensive data on global forest extent and changes from 2000 through 2023. Users can visualize, analyze, and download the dataset through several platforms:

- **Google Earth Engine** (developers.google.com)
- **Global Forest Change Portal**: Hosted by the **University of Maryland**, this portal offers direct downloads of various versions of the dataset, including the latest updates (<https://storage.googleapis.com/earthenginepartners-hansen/GFC-2023-v1.11/download.html>)

- **Global Forest Watch (GFW):** Managed by the World Resources Institute, GFW provides an interactive platform where users can explore the GFC data alongside other forest-related datasets, enabling dynamic visualization and analysis (globalforestwatch.org).

3.1.2 Strengths

- **Comprehensive Global Coverage:** Provides global-scale forest disturbance monitoring at a high spatial resolution (30 meters), enabling consistent tracking from 2000 through 2023.
- **Annual Updates:** Allows robust analysis of long-term forest trends, essential for monitoring and policy comparisons.
- **High Accessibility:** Integration with Google Earth Engine provides an open and user-friendly online platform, widely accessible for researchers, policymakers, and conservation managers.
- **High Accuracy:** Achieves balanced user's and producer's accuracies greater than 80% across all climate domains, ensuring reliable detection of forest loss. It shows higher accuracy levels in boreal and temperate forests compared to tropical regions, where forest gain classification shows greater variability. This highlights the dataset's reliability in tracking disturbances in boreal and temperate ecosystems.
- **Precise Temporal Validation:** MODIS NDVI validation showed that 75.2% of forest loss events match precisely to the year of disturbance, with 96.7% accuracy within one year; additionally supported by NASA's GLAS LiDAR validation, confirming accurate detection through canopy height measurements (Hansen, et al 2013).
- **Enhanced Detection Sensitivity:** Version 1.11 integrates improved data from Landsat 8 (2013 onward) and Landsat 9 (2022 onward), providing higher signal-to-noise ratios compared to earlier sensors.
- **Improved Disturbance Detection:** Recent methodological updates significantly enhanced detection capabilities, especially for:
 - Boreal forest disturbances caused by fire.
 - Smallholder agricultural clearing in tropical dry and humid forests.
 - Selective logging activities.
 - Short-cycle plantation clearing within subtropical and tropical ecozones.
- **Increased Temporal Consistency:** The number of available Landsat images per year has grown significantly to over 250,000 annually, ensuring more robust temporal consistency and finer spatial detail.

3.1.3 Limitations

- **No Disturbance Cause Attribution:** The dataset does not differentiate between disturbance types (e.g., fire, logging, storms), limiting its ability to provide detailed ecological interpretations and targeted management responses.

- **Limited Detection of Partial Canopy Loss:** It primarily detects stand-replacement disturbances, making it ineffective for tracking selective logging, gradual canopy decline, and forest degradation processes.
- **Uncertainty in Forest Gain Detection:** Forest gain classification has significant variability, particularly in tropical regions, and a high uncertainty range.
- **Higher False Positives in Certain Ecosystems:** The dataset exhibits elevated false positive rates in regions with seasonal vegetation changes, such as drylands and mixed forest-grassland ecosystems, potentially misclassifying temporary canopy fluctuations as deforestation.
- **Inconsistencies Due to Sensor Transitions:** Differences between Landsat 7 (affected by scan-line errors post-2002) and newer Landsat 8 and 9 data introduce discrepancies, particularly before and after 2013, affecting the consistency of long-term analyses.
- **Temporal Inconsistencies in Data Processing:** Reprocessing from 2011 onward has improved recent data consistency, but earlier years remain uncorrected, leading to inconsistencies that complicate trend analyses. Algorithmic modifications, including changes in training datasets and classification approaches, further contribute to year-to-year variations.
- **Pending Validation with Newer Landsat Data:** A full validation incorporating Landsat 8 and 9 has not yet been completed, meaning additional methodological sensitivities could emerge, potentially affecting accuracy and long-term consistency.

3.2 European Forest Disturbance Atlas (EFDA)

The **European Forest Disturbance Atlas (EFDA)** (Viana-Soto & Senf, 2024) is a **pan-European dataset** that provides **annual forest disturbance maps** across **38 European countries** from **1985 to 2023**. It is designed to capture **multiple disturbance events per pixel** and attribute them to specific causes such as **fire, windthrow, bark beetle outbreaks, and harvesting**.

Despite previous efforts to map forest change, existing datasets lack **multi-disturbance tracking** and long-term consistency. The **EFDA fills this gap** by offering an **annual, high-resolution, and multi-agent disturbance dataset**.

EFDA employs a **consistent Landsat time-series approach** to track disturbances with a **30-m spatial resolution**. The dataset includes multiple layers, such as **disturbance occurrence, severity, frequency, and agent classification**, making it particularly useful for **forest management, policy planning, and ecological research**. Its **open-access and automated processing workflow** ensures regular updates and reproducibility.

3.2.1 Methodology

EFDA follows a **classification-based machine learning approach**, leveraging **Landsat time-series data** for automated disturbance detection. The process can be divided into the following **key steps** (Viana-Soto & Senf, 2024):

1. Landsat Data Cube and Processing

- The **study area** covers **5.75 million km²** (excluding Russia, Malta, Cyprus, and overseas territories).
- A **Landsat data cube** was created for Europe, storing **115,663 images** (Landsat 4–9) from **1984 to 2023** in a structured, tiled format (150 x 150 km).
- Images were selected based on **cloud cover** (<60%) and restricted to the **growing season** (June 1 – September 30) to ensure spectral consistency.
- Images were processed to **surface reflectance (Level-2)** using the **FORCE software**, which applies:
 - **Atmospheric correction** with a precompiled water vapor database.
 - **Topographic normalization** using the ASTER Global Digital Elevation Model.
 - **Cloud and shadow masking**, employing a modified **Fmask algorithm**.
 - **Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function** (BRDF) correction to normalize illumination effects.
- The **Landsat data cube structure** ensures consistent, gap-free, and cloud-free image composites, improving long-term monitoring.

2. Best Available Pixel (BAP) Compositing

- Annual, **cloud-free composites** were created using the **Best Available Pixel (BAP)** approach.
- Selection criteria included **distance to clouds**, **haze opacity**, and **proximity to August 1st**.
- **Gap-filling interpolation** was applied to reduce missing data from **10.1% to 4.9% per year**.

3. Forest Land Use Mask

- A **random forest model** classified pixels as **forest or non-forest** based on multi-year Landsat data.
- **FAO's forest land use definition** was used, including temporarily unstocked and reforested areas.

EFDA detects forest disturbances by applying a **Random Forest classification model** trained on reference samples of known disturbances. The detection process follows these key steps:

1. **Baseline Spectral Analysis** – Annual composite images are analyzed for spectral deviations using key vegetation indices such as **NDVI**, **NBR**, and **Tasseled Cap components**.

2. **Machine Learning Classification** – A trained classifier differentiates between undisturbed forest and various disturbance types based on spectral characteristics.
3. **Multi-Year Disturbance Tracking** – EFDA allows for the detection of **multiple disturbances per pixel**, tracking changes across different years to identify recurring events. This multi-year tracking approach ensures that disturbances are not only captured at their initial occurrence but also monitored over time, revealing long-term patterns in forest dynamics.

4. Annual Disturbance Detection

- Disturbances are mapped using a **random forest classification model**, trained on:
 - **Spectral indices** (NDVI, NBR, Tasseled Cap)
 - **Multi-year spectral change (t0 vs. t-1)**
- **SMOTE balancing** was applied to correct for sample imbalance (disturbances = ~3% of pixels).
- Post-processing included:
 - **Applying a minimum mapping unit (0.27 ha)**
 - **Collapsing disturbances** occurring within **4-year intervals** to prevent over-counting

5. Disturbance Agent Classification

Based on spectral characteristics, the trained classifier differentiates between undisturbed forest and various disturbance types. To assign disturbance types, EFDA integrates both spectral analysis and external validation datasets:

- **Wildfires:** Confirmed using burned area spectral signatures and cross-validation with **EFFIS (European Forest Fire Information System)**.
- **Windthrow:** Identified based on abrupt spectral changes in canopy structure, validated with national forest inventory reports.
- **Bark Beetle Outbreaks:** Detected using progressive spectral degradation patterns, typically associated with tree mortality trends.
- **Harvesting:** Differentiated from natural disturbances using characteristic temporal patterns and ancillary land-use data.

A **random forest model** classified disturbances using **18 predictors**, including **patch size, spectral changes, and landscape context**.

The **agent attribution model** groups disturbed pixels into **three categories**:

- **Windthrow / Bark Beetle (combined),**
- **Fire** and
- **Harvest** (including both planned timber harvesting and removals of damaged trees following natural disturbance)

The **beetle and windthrow** were merged into a single category due to **high confusion** between spectral and structural patterns. **Harvest disturbances** were identified by **selecting a random background sample**, assuming **most European disturbances are harvest-related**.

According to **Viana-Soto & Senf (2024)**, the model predicting the disturbance agent had an **overall error** rate of 14.1%, with the following a commission and omission error rates:

- **Windthrow/Bark Beetle (combined): 10.5% commission, 19.1% omission**
- **Fire: 5.7% commission, 25.5% omission**
- **Harvest: 17.4% commission, 8.7% omission**

7. Accuracy Assessment

According to **Viana-Soto & Senf (2024)**, EFDA disturbance maps achieve high accuracy in detecting disturbances (F1-score: 0.89) and forest land use (F1-score: 0.92), Errors decrease over time, with commission errors reducing from 22.5% (1985–1990) to 10.6% (after 2000). Regarding discrimination between non-forest and forest land use, it also yielded high accuracies (overall F1-score of 0.92, with F1-scores of 0.93 for non-forest and 0.91 for forest land use).

8. Final Product Layers

The EFDA provides **30m-resolution layers** at the **country level**. The maps are available per country as **GeoTIFF**. The spatial reference system is **EPSG 3035 (ETRS89 / LAEA Europe)**.

- **Forest land use mask:** Identifies Forest areas based on FAO criteria.
- **Annual disturbance:** Binary map (0 = undisturbed, 1 = disturbed).
- **Disturbance probability:** Probability of disturbance occurrence (0–100).
- **Latest disturbance year:** Year of the most recent disturbance per pixel.
- **Greatest disturbance year:** Year of the disturbance with the highest severity.
- **Number of disturbances:** Number of times a pixel was disturbed (1–4+).
- **Disturbance severity:** Spectral change in NBR ($t - t-1$).
- **Disturbance agent:** Annual classification: (1 = Wind/Bark Beetle, 2 = Fire, 3 = Harvest).
- **Aggregated disturbance agent:** Summarizes dominant disturbance agent over time ((1 = Wind/Bark Beetle, 2 = Fire, 3 = Harvest). If multiple agents are detected, class 4 (Mixed) is assigned.

9. Access

The EFDA dataset is **openly accessible to the public** via Zenodo. (<https://zenodo.org/records/13333034>). The maps can also be explored online (<https://albaviana.users.earthengine.app/view/european-forest-disturbance-map>).

3.2.2 Strengths

- **Long-term Temporal Coverage:** EFDA covers **38 years (1985–2023)**, making it one of Europe's longest-running forest disturbance datasets.
- **Consistent and Automated Processing:** Using **Landsat data cubes** and **automated machine learning workflows** ensures **scalability and reproducibility**.
- **Open Access and Reproducibility:** EFDA is designed as an **open-source dataset**, facilitating its use in research, conservation, and policy-making.
- **Detection of Recurring Disturbances:** Unlike many products that detect only a single disturbance event per pixel, EFDA identifies **multiple events over time**, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of **recurring disturbances and forest recovery dynamics**. Compared to previous datasets (Hansen et al. 2013, Senf & Seidl 2021a, Turubanova et al. 2023), EFDA detects 30–40% more disturbances due to its ability to track multiple events per pixel, improved accuracy (lower omission error), and broader forest definition. This makes it one of the most comprehensive forest disturbance datasets available for Europe.
- **Disturbance Agent Classification:** The ability to differentiate between **fire, windthrow - bark beetle outbreaks (combined category), and harvest** provides **valuable insights for forest management and policy decisions**.
- **Reliable Detection Performance:** With an **F1-score of 0.89**, EFDA demonstrates **strong classification accuracy** in identifying forest disturbances.
- **Comprehensive Validation:** Cross-referenced with **national forest inventories, LUCAS field surveys, and external disturbance records**, ensuring high reliability.

3.2.3 Limitations

- **Limited to Europe:** EFDA is **not applicable outside Europe**, restricting its use for global forest disturbance analysis.
- **Higher Classification Errors in Early Data (1985–2000):** Accuracy improvements are noticeable over time, but errors are **higher in early Landsat data** due to sensor limitations and atmospheric effects.
- **Limited Sensitivity to Low-Severity Disturbances:** EFDA may fail to detect **selective logging, understory removal, or low-intensity mortality** events, as they do not always cause significant spectral changes.
- **Potential Misclassification in Complex Landscapes:** Variability in **forest composition, land-use history, and spectral signatures** can introduce **classification errors**, particularly in mixed-use landscapes where natural and managed forests coexist. For instance, areas with a patchwork of managed plantations and semi-natural forests may exhibit spectral similarities that make distinguishing between harvesting and natural disturbances challenging.

- **30m Resolution Constraints: Small-scale disturbances** such as selective logging or undergrowth removal may be underrepresented, particularly in **fragmented landscapes** or areas with **fine-scale management practices**.
- **Dependence on Cloud-Free Observations:** Persistent cloud cover in certain regions (e.g., northern Europe and mountainous areas) reduces **data availability**, leading to **temporal gaps** in the dataset.
- **Gap-Filling Limitations:** Although linear interpolation helps mitigate missing data, it does not fully reconstruct spectral trends in persistently cloudy areas.
- **Commission and Omission Errors:**
 - Commission errors (**false positives**): Some areas with temporary canopy reductions (e.g., **agricultural clearings** or **seasonal** vegetation changes) may be mistakenly classified as disturbances.
 - Omission errors (**false negatives**): **low-severity (small or gradual) disturbances** may not trigger classification thresholds, leading to underestimation in some forest types.
- Challenges in **Mixed-Use Landscapes:** Areas with a mosaic of natural forests, managed plantations, and agricultural land may exhibit similar spectral signatures, increasing misclassification risks.
- **Harvest Disturbance Estimation is Indirect:** The classification of **harvest (logging) disturbances** is based on **random sampling assumptions**, rather than direct ground truthing.
- **Limited Ground Validation for Disturbance Attribution:** While EFDA integrates multiple external datasets, certain disturbances (e.g., **bark beetle outbreaks** or **windthrow events**) may require **additional ground-truthing** for improved classification accuracy.

3.3 Alert and Annual Changes System (AACS)

The **Alert and Annual Changes System (AACS)** is a **national-scale monitoring framework** that comprises **two complementary datasets**, each serving distinct purposes:

- **Monthly and Annual Alerts on Forest Surface (MAAFS)** (known in Spanish as *Alertas mensuales y anuales sobre la superficie forestal*) – Focuses on **real-time detection of vegetation disturbances**, issuing **monthly and annual alerts** for vegetation loss.
- **Annual Changes in Forest Surface (ACFS)** (known in Spanish as *Cambios anuales sobre la superficie forestal*) – Integrates **annual alerts and additional geospatial data** to monitor **both forest losses and vegetation recovery** over time.

Both datasets are part of **Spain's Territorial Information Subsystem** (*Subsistema de Información Territorial*), utilizing **Sentinel-2 imagery** and **NDVI anomaly detection** to assess vegetation activity. While **MAAFS enables rapid disturbance detection**, **ACFS offers a broader perspective**, capturing **long-term forest dynamics**, including deforestation (change from forest to non-forest use), silvicultural activities, wildfire damage, and regrowth.

Considering their **specific objectives and methodologies**, these datasets will be **analyzed individually in the subsequent sections**.

3.3.1 Monthly and Annual Alerts on Forest Surface within the AACs framework

The **Monthly and Annual Alerts on Forest Surface (MAAFS)** is a **nationwide monitoring system** that tracks **vegetation disturbances across Spain**. Using **Sentinel-2 satellite imagery**, it detects **significant changes in vegetation activity**, issuing **monthly and annual alerts** for **vegetation vigor loss and wildfires**. The system operates at a **high spatial resolution of 25x25 meters**, aligning with the **Spanish Inventory of Natural Heritage and Biodiversity (IEPNB) grid**.

3.3.1.1 Methodology

1. Data Processing and Preprocessing

MAAFS processes **Sentinel-2 MSI Level-2A imagery**, applying **atmospheric and radiometric corrections** for accuracy. Unreliable pixels (affected by **clouds, shadows, and snow**) are **masked** using **Sentinel-2's Cloud Probability dataset** and the **Scene Classification Layer (SCL)**.

A **data availability index** is created to improve consistency, excluding pixels with **less than 50% valid observations** from analysis.

Significant Vegetation Anomaly Detection

MAAFS detects vegetation anomalies by **comparing the monthly maximum NDVI value** to a **historical reference period**. An anomaly is **considered significant** only if it meets **both** of the following conditions:

1. **Standardized NDVI Anomaly < -3** – Assesses **how far NDVI departs from historical averages** in standard deviations. Values falling below **-3** highlight significant **vegetation loss**.
2. **Absolute NDVI Anomaly < -0.15 to -0.25** – Calculates the **direct NDVI difference** from the historical average, confirming that observed changes are substantial **rather than trivial fluctuations**.

This dual approach ensures that **only persistent and extreme vegetation declines** are flagged, reducing false detections.

2. Filtering and False Positive Reduction

To enhance accuracy, MAAFS applies **additional spectral indices**:

- **MNDWI (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index)** – Eliminates **false positives** from **water bodies, fog, and cloud shadows**.

- **BAIS2 (Burn Area Index for Sentinel-2)** – Improves **fire detection accuracy**, preventing misclassification in **dark soils, volcanic terrain, and shaded slopes**.

3. Classifying Wildfire Disturbances

Fire-affected pixels are classified based on a structured validation process that integrates multiple data sources. The classification of wildfire anomalies is generated by spatially **cross-referencing pixels identified as fire-affected by BAIS2** with the **monthly aggregated data from EFFIS (European Forest Fire Information System) and FIRMS (Fire Information for Resource Management System) fire hotspots**.

This method ensures that detected vegetation loss is attributed to wildfire events rather than other disturbances. **EFFIS burned area maps** validate the extent of detected fires, while **FIRMS** provides **real-time data on active fire locations**. Additionally, the **Spanish Forest Map (MFE)** and **Fixed Photo Dataset (FF)** help distinguish burned forested areas from other types of vegetation losses.

By incorporating this multi-step approach, MAAFS distinguishes **wildfire disturbances** from **other vegetation losses**, reducing misclassification errors and improving the reliability of the alerts.

4. Classification and Alert Generation

Based on detected anomalies, **monthly alerts** are categorized into:

- Current month fire events
- Fires from the previous six months
- Vegetation vigor loss in tree formations
- Vegetation vigor loss in non-tree formations
- Stable areas (no significant changes)
- No data available (insufficient quality observations)

Tree and non-tree formations are classified according to the **Spanish Forest Map (MFE)**.

Annual alerts are generated by consolidating monthly detections, confirming vegetation loss only if anomalies persist for at least three consecutive months ensuring sustained disturbances are identified. The annual alert classifications include:

- Fire events
- Vegetation vigor loss in tree formations
- Vegetation vigor loss in non-tree formations

Additionally, annual alerts contain information on the start and end of each disturbance event and the number of months it remained active.

5. Final Product Layers Access

Example for year 2023:

- Annual Alerts for 2023 (with the following classes :Fire; Loss of Vegetation Vigor)
- Monthly Alerts for 2023 (with the following classes: Stable,Fire, Loss of Vegetation Vigor, No Data)

6. Access

The monthly alerts from the MAAFS dataset are available upon request to the Information System of the Inventory of Natural Heritage and Biodiversity (IEPNB). The annual alerts are available open-access via the Territorial information subsystem from IEPNB portal (<https://iepnb.es/veikos/>).

3.3.1.2 Strengths

- **High temporal resolution and near real-time monitoring** – MAAFS enables continuous forest disturbance tracking through monthly alerts, providing **early warnings for land managers and policymakers**.
- **Automated and scalable processing** – The cloud-based workflow ensures **systematic and reproducible data processing**, minimizing manual intervention while maintaining **national-scale coverage**.
- **Robust classification of wildfire events** – The integration of **EFFIS, FIRMS, and BAIS2** enhances the accuracy of fire disturbance detection, reducing misclassification errors.
- **Advanced spectral filtering** – The integration of **MNDWI and BAIS2** significantly enhances classification accuracy by removing false positives associated with **water bodies, fog, cloud shadows, and non-fire vegetation disturbances**.
- **Noise reduction through NDVI composites** – The use of **monthly maximum NDVI values** reduces the impact of **cloud cover and atmospheric artifacts**, improving data reliability.
- **Long-term change analysis** – The consolidation of **monthly alerts into annual summaries** enables **trend analysis** in forest degradation, deforestation, and regeneration processes.

3.3.1.3 Limitations

- **Lack of causal attribution for non-fire disturbances** – While **wildfire-related vegetation loss is well-differentiated**, MAAFS does not **directly classify other disturbance causes** (e.g., droughts, pests, or logging), requiring external validation.
- **Absence of ground-truth validation, especially for non-fire disturbances** – The system does not incorporate photointerpretation for independent validation, necessitating **cross-referencing with external datasets** for confirmation.
- **Potential time lag in detection** – Due to **monthly maximum NDVI values**, some disturbances may only appear **in the following month's dataset**.

- **Cloud cover interference** – In **persistently cloudy regions (e.g., northern Spain, mountainous areas, and the Canary Islands)**, disturbance detection may be underestimated due to limited cloud-free observations.
- **Overestimation in semi-arid regions** – NDVI fluctuations in **grasslands and dehesas** may be misinterpreted as vegetation loss due to **seasonal variations**, rather than actual forest degradation.

3.3.2 Annual Changes in Forest Surface (ACFS) within the AACCS framework

The **Annual Changes in Forest Surface (ACFS)** dataset provides a **comprehensive annual assessment** of **significant vegetation changes** within Spain's forested areas. Unlike **MAAFS**, which focuses on **short-term forest disturbances**, **ACFS tracks both vegetation losses and gains**, allowing for **long-term monitoring** of **forest degradation, reforestation, and afforestation processes**.

3.3.2.1 Methodology

1. Data Sources and Preprocessing

ACFS integrates data from **MAAFS annual alerts** and geospatial datasets, including:

- **Sentinel-2 MSI Level-2A imagery** (Harmonized Sentinel-2 MSI Collection, processed to Bottom-Of-Atmosphere (BOA) reflectance).
- **European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS)** – Provides information on burned forest areas.
- **FIRMS (Fire Information for Resource Management System)** – Identifies active fire hotspots.
- **Spanish Forest Map (MFE)** and **Fixed Photo Dataset (FF)** – Used to define forested areas and validate detected changes.
- **SIGPAC (Agricultural Parcel Geographic Information System)** – Detects land-use changes between forests and other land categories.

All input data undergoes **preprocessing** to correct for atmospheric effects, align spatial resolution, and mask low-quality pixels (e.g., clouds, snow, and shadow-affected areas).

2. Change Detection Process

- **Vegetation Loss Detection:** Annual vegetation loss is identified through a **frequency-based consolidation of monthly alerts**, ensuring that only **persistent changes** are classified. A loss is confirmed if:
 - The detected anomaly **persists for at least three consecutive months**.
 - The affected area falls within **forested land as defined by MFE and SIGPAC**.
 - There is **no subsequent NDVI recovery** that suggests seasonal fluctuations rather than true vegetation loss.

- **Vegetation Gain Detection:** Vegetation gains are assessed by identifying areas where NDVI values indicate **sustained recovery** following previous vegetation loss. Gains are only detected in **areas classified as forest loss** in the most recent **Fixed Photo Dataset (FF)**.
 - The **Tau-Kendall trend analysis** is applied to NDVI time series over multiple years to determine **significant increasing trends (p-value < 5%)**. This indicates a **consistent increase in vegetative activity**, signifying natural recovery or managed afforestation.
 - Due to **Sentinel-2's spatial resolution (10–20 meters per pixel)**, it is **not possible to distinguish between natural vegetation recovery and active afforestation/reforestation**. Thus, all vegetation gains are classified under a single category.

3. Classification of Annual Changes

ACFS categorizes detected changes into four main classes:

- **Logging (Silvicultural Operations)** – Identifies tree felling in forested areas, typically associated with thinning, clear-cutting, or selective logging.
- **Deforestation** – Detects areas where forest land has been permanently converted to **agriculture, artificial surfaces, or water bodies**, based on SIGPAC classifications.
- **Wildfire Damage** – Identifies burned areas, categorized into:
 - **Forest (FA – Densely forested areas)**
 - **Sparse Forest (FAr – Open-canopy forest)**
 - **Non-Forest (FD – Shrublands, grasslands, and other low vegetation)**
- **Vegetation Gains** – Includes afforestation, reforestation, or natural regeneration in areas previously affected by forest loss.

4. Validation and Quality Control

A **photointerpretation process** is performed to verify ACFS classifications. This includes:

- **Random sampling (10%) of polygons larger than 1 hectare** for manual verification.
- **Cross-validation with Sentinel-2 imagery (summer and autumn observations)** from the current and previous years.
- **Comparison with high-resolution PNOA orthophotos** to ensure consistency.

If the **classification accuracy does not meet an 80% threshold**, the dataset is manually refined to correct major misclassifications.

5. Final Product Layers

Example for year 2023:

- Classified **Annual Alerts 2023: Gain** (with the following classes)
 - Alert: Logging of evolving densely forested areas (brown)
 - Alert: Wildfire in evolving densely forested areas (green)
 - Alert: Wildfire in evolving sparsely forested areas (yellow)
- Classified **Annual Alerts 2023: Losses** (with the following classes)
 - Alert: Conversion of densely forested areas to non-forest
 - Alert: Conversion of sparsely forested areas to non-forest
 - Alert: Wildfire in densely forested areas
 - Alert: Wildfire in sparsely forested areas

6. Access

The ACFS dataset is available open-access via the Territorial information subsystem from IEPNB portal (<https://iepnb.es/veikos/>).

3.3.2.2 Strengths

- **Comprehensive monitoring:** ACFS tracks **both losses and gains**, providing a **complete assessment of forest dynamics**.
- **Integration of multiple reference datasets:** Cross-validation with **MFE, FF, SIGPAC, EFFIS, and FIRMS** improves classification reliability.
- **Automated processing with photointerpretation validation:** While primarily automated, ACFS includes **manual verification of sampled areas**, balancing **scalability with accuracy**.
- **Detection of vegetation recovery trends** – The application of **Tau-Kendall trend analysis** enables the identification of **long-term forest regeneration**, aiding in monitoring **afforestation and reforestation efforts and natural regeneration trends**.
- **Standardized national framework** – The use of **harmonized classification criteria** ensures consistency with **national and European forest monitoring initiatives**.

3.3.2.3 Limitations

- **Sentinel-2 Resolution Limitations in Detecting Fine-Scale Vegetation Changes** – The **spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 (10–20m per pixel)** constrains ACFS's ability to detect **small-scale vegetation dynamics**, particularly in fragmented or heterogeneous landscapes. This limitation affects the **differentiation of natural regeneration from human-driven afforestation or reforestation**, as both processes often occur at scales smaller than Sentinel-2's detection threshold. As a result, **all vegetation gains are classified under a single category**, reducing the precision of forest recovery assessments. Additionally, in areas with **patchy regrowth or young plantations**, the system may fail to capture subtle canopy developments, further complicating accurate classification of vegetation recovery.

- **Misclassification of Seasonal Changes as Permanent Vegetation Loss or Gain** – In **semi-arid and grassland ecosystems**, **seasonal NDVI fluctuations due to periodic greening and senescence** can lead to **misidentification of short-term changes as long-term forest loss or gain**. This may cause **overestimation or underestimation** of actual vegetation cover changes, particularly in areas with **high natural variability in plant growth cycles**.
- **Challenges in Detecting Early-Stage Vegetation Recovery** – Recently disturbed areas, such as those affected by **logging or wildfires**, often show **highly dynamic herbaceous growth**, making it difficult to differentiate **temporary seasonal regrowth from sustained long-term recovery**. This can lead to **misclassification errors**, particularly when early-stage vegetation exhibits **unstable spectral signals**.
- **Soil Reflectance Interference in Reforested Areas** – In **recently reforested zones**, the **small size of newly planted saplings** results in a spectral signal dominated by **bare soil reflectance rather than vegetation**, reducing detection accuracy. Consequently, ACFS may **underestimate reforestation efforts**, as early-stage tree plantations are often misclassified due to their **low canopy cover**.
- **Lower Classification Accuracy in Sparse Vegetation Areas** – In ecosystems with **low-density vegetation**, such as **open woodlands and early-stage regrowth sites**, the spectral signal may still be **heavily influenced by exposed soil**, leading to **misinterpretation of vegetation health and coverage**. This increases the likelihood of **false classifications** of both forest loss and recovery.
- **Underrepresentation of Natural Regeneration and Afforestation** – Due to classification challenges and Sentinel-2's resolution constraints, **both natural regeneration and afforestation efforts may be underreported or misclassified**. This impacts the **accuracy of long-term forest change assessments** and complicates efforts to **track reforestation progress at a national scale**.
- **Cloud Cover Interference** – Similar to **MAAFS**, **persistent cloud cover in mountainous and humid regions** reduces the availability of high-quality Sentinel-2 observations, leading to **potentially undetected vegetation changes** in affected areas.
- **Difficulty Detecting Selective Logging and Thinning** – ACFS is **optimized for large-scale disturbances**, making it **less effective at capturing small-scale forestry activities**, such as **selective logging, understory clearing, and gradual canopy degradation**. These changes often remain **undetected or misclassified**, limiting the system's ability to assess **sustainable forest management practices**.
- **Dependence on Historical Datasets for Reference Classification** – The accuracy of ACFS classifications **relies on external datasets** such as **MFE, FF, and SIGPAC**, which may not always reflect **recent land-use changes**. If these reference datasets **become outdated**, their integration into the ACFS workflow **may introduce classification errors**, particularly in rapidly changing landscapes.

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